

HISTORY OF UZBEK FOLKLORE GAMES AND THEIR PLACE IN CHILDREN'S LIVES

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ABSTRACT

This article serves to organize the history of the origin of national folk games, dances, physical exercises and national sports, as well as how important they are in society and reveals that the study, research and introduction of folklore games into the practice of educating young people is one of the main means of elevating our values, culture and spiritual riches.

A game is a historically organized social event, an independent type of activity, unique to man. Play activities are very diverse: children's games with toys, board games, circle games, movement games, sports games. Play can be a means of self-knowledge, entertainment, recreation, physical and general social education, a means of sports. It plays an important role in the development of entertainment, recreation, spiritual, mental and physical strength and makes a great fortune on the go. The most common variety of games among adults and children, especially among teenagers and children, are action games. Historically, hunting games have played an important role in the lives of primitive hunters. Some sources say they will be held before the hunt, while others comment on the post-hunt games. If we take a closer look at this data, we can say that the

hunting games were held both before and after the hunt. Pre-game games - previously used as an exercise (checking the readiness for the hunt, mental and physical preparation for the hunt), and seriously specific small primitive people have learned to easily catch prey, to approach it, a mask for this wearing, practicing the appearance of an animal, its behavior and sound. In the course of such games, young people were also taught to hunt. For this reason, he served as a kind of school, on the one hand, helped to develop the skills of hunters, on the other hand, formed and developed in them the art of imitation. Post-hunting games hunting is successful can be analyzed as organized only at the end. Because the return of the loot, the feast, the joy, the celebration of the whole team.

Body part: In Central Asia, there were hunting games in the lives of primitive

people. Hundreds of thousands of pre-Pesertol (Middle Paleolithic) human bones were found in a cave in the Baysun Mountains of the Paleolithic period, stone tools found in a cave in the village of Amankoton in Samarkand. The stone carvings of deer and oxen in Khojakent village and many other archeological finds and elements of fine arts, including children's folklore games, not only testify to the fact that they have the simplest branches, it also helps determine the stages of birth. These photographs depict the ancient hunting, wildlife, and nature rituals of primitive people, and the wearing of masks from the skins of animals during hunting, on the one hand, in order not to frighten wild animals during the hunt, and, on the other hand, ethnographic as well as customs and values. Paintings in the caves of the Soymalitash mountain in Fergana (II-I centuries BC) show the hunting ceremonies, which are covered with animal skins. In order to approach a herd of animals, primitive man must imitate animals or birds, and for this they must learn their peculiarities, how they walk, how they feed on grass, how they fight with each other, how they run away, and even how they sound.

Finally, the conditions for hunting wild animals required man to be agile, brave and tireless, and to do so constantly. All this, in turn, led to the birth of pantomime movements and games, heroic dances that imitated physical-rhythmic or natural phenomena in primitive man. The image of the game in the pictures drawn on the rocks and caves has a different character in terms of content and form. Some are reminiscent of the process of hunting and labor, some in

the form of imitations of natural phenomena, while others are reminiscent of martial arts, magic, gestures, and the art of pantomime. In the early days, when noisy chaotic games were gradually replaced by musical pantomimes and plastic movements, games with such ethnographic interpretations took on different forms: 'Bear Game', 'Dev Game', 'Monkey Game', then 'Cat game', 'Horse game', 'Humor game', 'Goat game', 'Wolf game', 'Bitter game', 'Eagle game', 'Dog game (irillatar game)', 'Rabbit game', 'Fox game', 'Jacques-jack game' are known to be passed down from generation to generation. They are directly or indirectly related to children's folklore games. Thus, the word "game" is associated with the Turkic word for play (meaning home, mind, wisdom). The ability to express the mind through movement and gestures is important in the birth of games. The scope and style of performance of traditional Uzbek children's folklore games is very wide. Social life, there is no aspect of human relationships that is not in the spotlight of the games, whether it is the culture of agriculture, animal husbandry, horticulture, profession and science, philosophical, aesthetic, ethical or educational, moral views are all the subject of traditional games. In particular, Uzbek children's folklore games are full of spiritual, educational and moral concepts. Depending on the content of children's folklore games, which have come down to us over the thousands of years of history of our people, through repeated experiments, becoming integrated and perfect, can be divided into the following types: :

1. Seasonal children's folklore games: folklore games played in the first spring, summer, winter seasons.

2. Ritual children's folk games: rituals, customs, ceremonies, games played on traditional holidays.

3. Labor-related children's folklore games: 'land reclamation, driving', 'planting', 'melon', 'apricot picking', 'melon festival', 'pocket', 'Good-bye', 'churey-churey', 'cow milked', 'camel return', 'horse watering' and so on.

4. Family children's folk games: 'guest-guest', 'bride-to-be', 'bride-groom', 'mother-child', 'cooking', 'home furnishing', 'puppet show', 'bread-making', 'alla-alla', 'cradle-decoration', 'cradle-to-cradle' and others.

5. Folklore games for physically active children: 'chase', 'the bed is closed', 'smart', 'goose-goose', 'hase the ball', 'white bone', 'Ball', 'break', 'rattle', 'run', 'zuv-zuv', 'white poplar-blue poplar', 'donkey riding', 'lanka', 'horse game', 'Girl chased' and others.

6. Logical children's folk games: quick sayings, riddle finding games, sayings, questions and answers, guessing, memory recovery games, guesses, etc.

7. Children's folk games related to animals and natural phenomena.

8. Fun children's folk games.

9. Music games. Folk games, including children's folklore games, have developed and deepened since ancient times, combining the way of life, spiritual, educational, physical training, aesthetic worldview of the people. Unlike other arts, the games reflect the psyche, psychology and upbringing of the younger generation.

According to historical sources, in the late Paleolithic period (about 40-41 thousand years BC) the transition of ancient people to animal husbandry and agriculture in connection with the emergence of the totem division of labor in the north of the earth (this process in Central Asia in the late III millennium BC II the beginning of the millennium) began to create customs, rituals and games in this new field. It is known that the happiest event in the life of a farmer was the process of harvesting and tasting new delicacies. This year-round process has created a festive mood among farmers. In order to reflect such a high mood in the actions, people organized games and ceremonies, and 'labor games' created a festive mood, in a broad sense, with a good mood. With the advent of sedentary agriculture and its rapid development since the Bronze Age, the beginning of the labor season in the spring, the festivities and games dedicated to the end of the autumn harvest, thus became a tradition over the years. So, if the 'first profession' of man - on the basis of hunting - 'hunting games' has arisen, as a result of his transition to farming and engaging in it, 'labor games' are formed, and new labor games and holidays are celebrated. laid the groundwork for. Abu Rayhan Beruni's 'Monuments of Ancient Peoples' plays an important role. Especially during the Navruz holiday, various competitions and games such as 'kupkari', 'kurash', 'sowing', 'roosterfighting' and racing are considered to be the beauty of the holiday. There were also games of quail, rooster and ram fights. Therefore, the first examples of folk games are associated with human consciousness and thinking. The conditions of that period, people's hunting and living experiences, worldviews,

customs and rituals played a key role in its emergence. The first examples of a simple oral statement appeared. They were extremely simple, with a variety of exhortations and narratives. The process of hunting and the development of thinking led to the description of events and phenomena from a simple statement to a figurative description and wrote valuable insights into the national struggle. For example, he played the following games: 'Shooting from the bow', 'Chavgon games with small arms', 'Jumping on one leg', 'Jumping on something above', 'Shooting a spear', 'Stone shooting' and similar games. The people around him said that you are knowledgeable and intelligent, that you teach children various sciences and that you play with them. Ibn Sina commented that childhood was a game. Play activities in any form delight the child, active play with different moments of extraordinary joy, especially serves to evoke positive emotions. The tremendous educational power is the source of these 20 joyful emotions. N. K. Krupskaya repeatedly spoke about the great importance of games in the education of preschool children: 'Play is very important for preschoolers: play is a serious form of education for them.' N. K. Krupskaya also discusses the importance of play in physical development. There are many national games that develop physical fitness skills that improve vision and increase agility. It is extremely important to use all such things in preschools, which increase the agility of the target and are of great importance for labor. Any game, whether it is creative didactic music, is a unique tool for children to learn about the environment. The content of action games contains a lot of cognitive material that

expands the child's worldview and clarifies his imagination. The theme of the plot games is some episodes of human life, natural phenomena, animal habits. All this is reflected by children in a unique form of conditional play, but for the child to correctly perceive the outside world, it is necessary to know the characteristics and accuracy of the game situation. This is defined emotionally by the pedagogue in explaining the game. Folk games are a great example of this. The play situation in them warms and nurtures children, and the biologists encountered in some games directly characterize the characters and their actions. ('Falcon and turkey', 'Swans and geese', etc.) The rules are educational, they determine the course of the game. Children's movement activities are governed by their interpersonal interactions which help to cultivate moral and volitional qualities. In this case, the child can not stand without showing the qualities that are formed when guided by the game. For example, in a children's 'cunning fox' game, only after the fox says 'I'm here', you can get out of the circle and run in different directions. This rule helps children to develop attention, endurance, and quick reaction to a given signal in space. Proprietary emulsions help to overcome the need to follow the rules. 'Rule is the first stimulus that directs the movement of the child in accordance with the demands of the community. The first signs of deep friendship and love appear in the games perceived as a compulsory necessary response action that occurs during play development by more useful children in small groups (rabbits run through the bushes when bears appear, sparrows fly off the road when a car appears). Children are

first formed under the pedagogical guidance of the rules, and then under the influence of certain members of the community, who represent the social significance of the rules, at different times.

Eventually, the rules become a direct determinant of children's social norms of behavior. In addition, the pursuit of success and the easiest way to achieve it is also a violation of the rule. This, in turn, provokes dissatisfaction among the players, creates conflict and worsens the relationship between the children. The demands of adults are crucial for every child to understand and follow the rules of the game. Gradually, as a result of the educational impact, children's attitudes begin to change during play. There is an interest and aspiration to follow the rules and rules of the game a little more clearly. The reasons for not following the rules of the game will also change, and now children will break them unintentionally and immediately try to correct the mistake. Under the guidance of an educator who systematically prepares children to understand the social significance of rules, they become a means of cultivating good qualities such as honesty, fairness, courage, perseverance, and will. 'Such vital moral qualities, which are gradually acquired by the child, become the inner spiritual property of the child's personality.' All this serves as a basis for defining the rules of games as one of the most effective means of moral education of children. Memory ingenuity helps to develop thinking activity, so national action games help children develop mentally. Figurative emotional methodology plays an important role in improving the mental processes of children.

It is interesting and imaginative for children and encourages creative execution of difficult movements. Research by psychologists shows that a child learns to realize the reality of space and objects through play activities. At the same time, the mechanism of perception of space itself is greatly improved. Perception of space in the game manifests itself in its basic forms. Direct emotional cognition sensory (emotional-figurative) and indirect (logical thinking, perception), for example, the child's independent choice of direction of movement and the performance of the action in a direction strictly defined by the rules of the game.) and the immediate assessment of visual motor reaction (game movements) requires the other side to understand and imagine their actions from the spatial game environment and to demonstrate that visual reaction. In a moving game, these two components interact. The rules of the game, developed by the educator, provide the necessary opportunity for the child's movement to be pre-planned in space. At the same time, sudden changes in the game situation (starting action or signals) disrupt the action plan. Very complex children require quick reactions and targeting in space. 'Two frosts', 'Magic wand', 'Brave children', 'Monkeys and hunters' and others are examples of this. Such a reaction is determined by the level of development of children's ability to adapt their activities and movements to a particular environment. The educator gradually teaches the child to find a more successful way of acting, taking into account the situation of the game and the need to achieve the task. For example, when playing a game and checking in space, the child used

a quick and long run from the starter, showing agility and dexterity when standing close to him ('Trap', 'Cunning fox' and so on). Deliberate obstacles in the way of the game also help to target the environment ('Running across the flag to the flag', 'The wolf is with me', 'Brave children' and so on). This gives children the ability to evaluate an acceptable movement pattern with a sufficiently developed fall and make independent choices based on taking into account movements and timing of movements. It's a bit more complicated than the need to react quickly to a constantly changing game situation. A large group of children successfully master this skill in the process of repeating the game 'Trap', 'Cunning fox', 'Chase' and so on. In the national game, children practice determining the distance between objects and people. As a result, it develops visual assessment as well as spatial hearing ('Far Close', 'Sometimes Here, Sometimes Here', 'Eye Binding Game'). E.Ya.Stepanenkova's research shows that games determine children's understanding of intersubjective spatial relationships in front, back, middle,

left, above, below, intermediate side, opposite, sequence, and so on ('walk faster', 'knot', 'who is faster', 'run through the hoop to the flag', 'falcon and turkey', 'roll the ball between the latitudes' and so on).

Conclusion. At present, children are brought up in our country in the spirit of friendship and respect for the peoples and their art - songs, dances and games. Therefore, the choice of colorful folk movement games is necessary in the educational work with children, the application of moral patterns in the lives of children strengthens and a positive aesthetic attitude to folk art and, consequently, to its representatives. Famous educator K. Ushinsky appreciated moving games in a high level, and from them the wide range of activities in the upbringing of children, in any form, delight the child, and mobile play serves to evoke positive feelings in different situations of joy. The great educational power is the source of this joyful mood.

References

1. Usmonhojayev T.S., Khodjayev F. Action games. Tashkent, 1992.
2. Khojayev F. and others. national games of the people part 1. Tashkent, 2001.
3. Normurodov A.N. Uzbek national games. Tashkent, 1999.
4. Usmonhojayev T.S., Khodjayev F. Game "1001". 1990.
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On education" Tashkent East 1997